

RAPD (J-06) is faster than RFLP (MGR586) analysis, but it is less informative for phylogenetic analysis because fewer bands are produced for each isolate. Because corresponding groups of isolates are defined with

MGR586 and RAPD (J-06) for the Philippine isolates tested, we propose that the two methods be used together to improve the overall efficiency with which field populations of the pathogen can be analyzed. A preliminary survey using

RAPD can be used to group similar strains and reduce redundancy. All distinct groups can then be sampled adequately for MGR586 analysis to establish the relationships among strains and lineages. ■

Rice dwarf (RD), a new virus disease in the Philippines

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RD is a destructive virus disease that was known to occur only in temperate regions such as Japan, Korea, China, and Nepal.

RD disease symptoms were recently observed in ricefields in Midsayap, North Cotabato, Philippines. Infected plants showed stunting and fine chlorotic specks or streaks on leaf blades (Fig. 1). Most of the plants showing the chlorotic specks were also infected with tungro disease, which obscures the symptoms of RD. However, RD leaf symptoms were clearly visible in plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) only.

Serological tests and electron microscopy confirmed RD infection in plant samples collected from Midsayap. Leaf extracts from symptomatic leaves diluted up to a thousand times gave a strong positive reaction to RD virus

1. RDV-infected leaves showing chlorotic specks or streaks (right); healthy leaf (extreme left).

2. a) RDV particles (arrows); b) RDV and RTBV particles.

(RDV) antiserum in rapid immunofilter paper assay. Electron microscopic observations of clarified infected sap revealed the presence of RDV particles (Fig. 2a), the diameter of which (65 nm)

is about twice that of RTBV (Fig. 2b).

RD was reported in the Philippines in the past, but the case was later proven to be tungro. Hence, this is the first true identification of RD in the Philippines. ■

Integrated pest management—weeds

Weed control in upland ricefields of Karnataka

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Weeds are a big constraint to raising the average upland rice yield in Karnataka from the current low of about 1 t/ha. Hand weeding is very effective but requires a lot of labor, thus making it costly for the upland farmer. Suitable herbicides have not yet been found.

To determine effective and economical weed control practices, we experimented during 1989-91 kharif by combining herbicides or using them with cultural practices. Butachlor and pendimethalin were applied alone or in combination with 2,4-D or hand weeding (Table 1). A weed-free treatment, two hand weedings at 20 and 40 d after rice emergence (DE), and nonweeded treatment were used for comparison. Plots were hand weeded in the weed-free check.

The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design. Soil is silty clay loam with pH 7.0, 0.84% organic C, and

an average 0.6 kg P/ha and 114.1 kg K/ha. Avinash in 1989 and 1990 and IET5656 in 1991 were seeded at 100 kg/ha with a spacing of 20 cm between rows. Fertilizer was applied 100-10.9-20.7 kg NPK/ha.

We took weed samples from a 1-m² quadrat and weighed them at the heading stage of the grassy weeds. We recorded yield and yield components from a 5-m² net plot area. Common weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Panicum* spp., *Digitaria* sp., *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. rotundus*, *C. difformis*, *Cyanotis* spp., *Commelina benghalensis*, *Spilanthes paniculata*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, and *Eclipta prostrata*.

Table 1. Effect of weed control treatments on weed dry weight and grain yields in upland rice, Karnataka, India, 1989-91 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Weed dry weight (g/m ²)				Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1989	1990	1991	Mean	1989	1990	1991	Mean
Butachlor 2.0 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE	413	429	111	318	2.1	0.7	2.0	1.6
Butachlor 1.5 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 2,4-D 0.6 kg ai/ha at 25-30 DE	177	425	-	301	2.6	1.3	-	2.0
Butachlor 1.5 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 1 hand weeding at 25-30 DE	22	-	22	22	4.1	-	2.5	3.3
Pendimethalin 1.5 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE	312	328	89	243	1.9	0.7	1.6	1.4
Pendimethalin 1.0 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 2,4-D 0.6 kg ai/ha at 25-30 DE	155	176	96	142	3.0	2.3	1.9	2.4
Pendimethalin 1.0 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 1 hand weeding at 25-30 DE	47	-	24	36	4.1	-	2.2	3.2
Weed-free check	5	7	5	6	4.4	5.9	2.6	4.3
Two hand weedings at 20 and 40 DE	28	42	24	31	4.1	3.6	2.3	3.3
Nonweeded control	972	610	201	594	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.2
LSD (0.05)	78	164	24		0.7	0.5	0.4	

DE = days after emergence.

Neither butachlor nor pendimethalin, whether alone or combined with 2,4-D, effectively controlled weeds. However, when combined with one hand weeding at 25-30 DE, they controlled weeds as effectively as two hand weedings at 20 and 40 DE. When butachlor or pendimethalin were combined with one hand weeding, grain yields were on par with those of two hand weedings and greater than the treatments with no hand weeding (Table 1).

The cost of additional production over the nonweeded control was highest with the weed-free check, followed by butachlor + hand weeding, pendimethalin + hand weeding, and two hand weedings. The marginal benefit-to-cost ratio, however, was higher with herbicides combined with one hand weeding than with two hand weedings or in the weed-free check because of the higher weed control costs of the weedings (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Economics of weed control in upland rice, Karnataka, India, 1989-91 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Value of additional output ^b over nonweeded control				Cost of weed control ^c				Marginal benefit-to-cost ratio ^d			
	1989	1990	1991	Mean	1989	1990	1991	Mean	1989	1990	1991	Mean
Butachlor 2.0 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE	189	50	198	146	22	15	15	17	8.5	3.4	13.5	8.5
Butachlor 1.5 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 2,4-D 0.6 kg ai/ha at 25-30 DE	240	100	-	170	22	17	-	20	10.9	5.7	-	8.3
Butachlor 1.5 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 1 hand weeding at 25-30 DE	380	-	279	329	52	47	49	50	7.3	-	5.7	6.5
Pendimethalin 1.5 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE	177	54	146	126	33	28	33	31	5.3	1.9	4.4	3.9
Pendimethalin 1.0 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 2,4-D 0.6 kg ai/ha at 25-30 DE	276	180	185	214	28	25	28	27	10.0	7.3	6.7	8.0
Pendimethalin 1.0 kg ai/ha at 4-6 DE + 1 hand weeding at 25-30 DE	385	-	237	311	58	-	57	57	6.7	-	4.1	5.4
Weed-free check	413	475	294	394	142	143	145	144	2.9	3.3	2.0	2.7
Two hand weedings at 20 and 40 DE	381	291	252	308	96	99	102	99	4.0	2.9	2.5	3.1

^aDE = days after emergence.

^bProduction cost = \$111 54/t rough rice. ^cCost of inputs (\$) : butachlor = 4.04/liter, pendimethalin = 6.15/liter, 2,4-D = 3.35/liter, *A* class labor = 0.48/d, *B* class labor = 0.46/d.

^dMarginal B C =
$$\frac{\text{Value of additional output over nonweeded control}}{\text{Cost of weed control treatment}}$$